

FIRST PRESENTATION OF VALIAS PROJECT: VALORIZATION OF MARINE INVASIVE ALIEN SPECIES A PATHWAY TOWARDS THE PROTECTION OF EUROPEAN MARINE BIODIVERSITY: FROM DESTRUCTIVE INVADERS TO A SOURCE OF WEALTH

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Abstract

VALIAS project aims to match the need for managing the marine Invasive Alien Species (IAS) populations with the growing demand for marine derived-products. Under the frame of circular economy, the valorization of unexploited IAS feedstock can represent a sustainable strategy for the realization of a circular bio-economy, with the production of stable and safe food, fish feed and cosmetic ingredients. Various compounds with high commercial value obtained from fish and other IAS byproducts will be valorized. In this way, VALIAS will contribute to the control of IAS stocks and of their negative ecological and economic impact on biodiversity, ecosystem services, and health in European seas. VALIAS will bring together experts from the industry and academia, specialized in interdisciplinary research areas of Marine-Maritime Research, Aquaculture, Feed and Food technology and safety and Cosmetology. As a joint research and innovation project, it will develop a strong partnership involving eight partners from five EU countries (namely Greece, Cyprus, Italy, Ireland and Bulgaria) and with different technical backgrounds from the academic and non-academic sectors. The execution of the project and the knowledge sharing will be based on secondments (exchanges) of research and innovation staff with an in-built return mechanism strengthening collaborative research among the different countries and sectors.

Keywords: *Unexploited feedstock valorization, bioactive compounds, circular economy, new value chains, aquaculture, food industry, cosmetic industry*

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1. Introduction

The marine environment is constantly under anthropogenic pressure that imposes several threats on biodiversity. Amongst these pressures, the major drivers of biodiversity loss are overfishing, habitat degradation, pollution, climate change and biological invasions. Non-indigenous species (NIS), also known as alien species, are species that have been introduced into areas that are not native to them (Kahrić *et al.* 2022; Hald-Mortensen 2023). It is estimated that fish invasions have caused at least \$37.08 billion in economic loss worldwide, from just 27 reported species (Haubrock *et al.* 2022). Overall, more than 1000 NIS are found in the European Seas (Galanidi *et al.* 2023). The vast majority of European marine NIS have their native distribution in the Western and Central Indo-Pacific, being mostly associated with introductions into the Mediterranean sea through the Suez Canal (Galanidi *et al.* 2023).

VALIAS as an international multidisciplinary consortium that aims to pioneer a responsible and integrated approach to control the population of IAS in European seas. The main goal of this project is to bridge the growing gap between resource scarcity and the demands of a growing population, within the scope of European initiatives. VALIAS project can turn the current problem of potential marine IAS into a "Win-Win" solution both for the European fisheries and for the companies active in the sector of food processing, aquaculture, nutrition and cosmetology.

Beyond the innovation it can bring to the afore mentioned sectors by opening a new market of innovative formulations based on unique products origin, their exploitation is expected to create a new type of fishery that will bring economic returns benefits to the professional fishers themselves. Furthermore, VALIAS will contribute to the exploitation of IAS stocks as a mitigation measure with respect to their negative ecological and economic impacts on biodiversity, ecosystem services, and health in European seas.

The VALIAS project, with 8 partners collaborating across 5 European countries, has secured a €1.5 million EU contribution for its 48-month duration. This initiative focuses on delivering innovative solutions for the control of marine European Invasive Alien Species (IAS) populations. Organized into 7 work packages, the project is structured to achieve 16 specific deliverables and milestones. With a total of 318 secondment months planned across partner institutions, the project aims to foster knowledge exchange and expertise dissemination, contributing to the effective management and conservation of marine biodiversity.

2. Material and Methods

VALIAS Objectives

Developing novel methods to utilize invasive alien species (IAS) is a crucial approach to improve population control and protect marine biodiversity in Europe. This effort aims to convert the existing problem caused by possible marine invasive alien species (IAS) into a mutually beneficial solution, benefiting both European fisheries and firms involved in aquaculture, nutrition, and cosmetics industries. This approach aims to enhance the productivity of European fisheries, aquaculture, food, and cosmetic sectors by meeting consumers' demands for chemical-free, high-quality, natural, and sustainable products. Additionally, it addresses the need for managing invasive alien species populations and fulfilling the increasing demand for marine-derived ingredients. These activities aim to obtain support for environmental, economic, and social aspects, promoting a comprehensive approach to marine conservation and economic growth.

VALIAS will address critical issues

The main goal is to enhance the comprehension of the biological needs of species, as required by the European Directive 1143/2014, which focuses on preventing and managing the introduction and proliferation of non-native species. To ensure the preservation of EU maritime biodiversity, protect human health, and strengthen local European coastal economies, especially the fisheries and aquaculture sectors, it is crucial to avoid the uncontrolled spread of Non-Indigenous Species (NIS) and specifically Invasive Alien Species (IAS).

To meet the increasing need for marine bioactive chemicals in the food, feed, and cosmetic industries in a sustainable and cost-effective way, it is necessary to create effective strategies for managing and controlling invasive alien species. Additionally it is important to make better use of plentiful but currently underutilized resources. The inclusion of functional ingredients in processed products requires the use of innovative and eco-friendly methods to extract the compounds efficiently. Additionally, it involves creating safe and stable ingredients with improved biological effects, absorption, and controlled release for various industry sectors.

The progress of technical and scientific knowledge in aquaculture is crucial for minimizing environmental impact, decreasing reliance on fishmeal and oils, promoting sustainable resource utilization, and enhancing animal welfare. This ultimately leads to the development of innovative and sustainable production methods for fish feed. The current urgency to seek sustainable and eco-friendly solutions highlights the need for precise and mandatory goals in these efforts.

VALIAS Implementation

In order to achieve the VALIAS strategy, a project duration of 48 months with five technical work packages (WPs) and 16 deliverables is foreseen. Researchers and scientific staff from a total of eight Partners of five European countries (namely Greece, Cyprus, Italy, Ireland and Bulgaria) will take part into 318 secondment months and implement the following steps:

- i. Marine IAS selection. Data collections and mapping.

Within the VALIAS project, a set of 6 IAS was a-priori selected, based on their invasion status, abundance and existing knowledge, to be explored for potential use in the food, feed and cosmetic industry. Those are: the red harpoon weed (*Asparagopsis armata*), the slipper limpet (*Crepidula fornicata*), the silvercheeked toadfish (*Lagocephalus sceleratus*), the rabbitfishes (*Siganus spp.*), the cornetfish (*Fistularia commersonii*), and long-spined sea urchin (*Diadema setosum*). In this step, (a) additional species that might also be of interest will be defined, (b) the existing information on all species, in terms of presence (distribution), abundance, biology, ecology, toxicity and uses (i.e., as fresh food, in food and feed industry) will be explored.

- ii. Extraction of valuable compounds by means of green extraction methods from underexploited feedstock biomass - Evaluation of toxicity and safety of ingredients.

The actions implemented within this step will be: i) Optimizing the recovery of valuable compounds from selected IAS through green extraction methods and their isolation in high purity, targeting to high yielding and selectivity. ii) Pressurised liquid extraction (PLE), Ultrasound (UAE) and Microwave assisted (MAE) will be applied for the recovery of bioactive compounds from selected species.

- iii. Encapsulation of bioactive compounds developing stable and safe formulations.

Innovative and efficient encapsulation techniques (electrospraying and spray drying) of bioactive compounds using proteins and / or polysaccharide mixture derived from the selected IAS and other marine and/or non-marine sources as carriers, in order to increase their bioactivity and controlled release, developing stable and safe formulations.

- iv. Development of stable and safe functional food, fish feed and cosmetic products. Implementation of preliminary market research for VALIAS products.

Encapsulated valuable compounds (collagen, chitosan, polysaccharides, omega-3 fatty acids, proteins, peptides, phenolic compounds, toxins) will be added in food, aquafeed and cosmetic products. The new agents will combine a wide range of functionality substituting the unsustainable and costly conventional raw materials, resulting in new and sustainable added value final products that meets consumers' needs.

- v. Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) to assess the environmental impact of processes and new products - Socio-techno-economic assessment of processes for final product development.

The combination of LCA with financial data and economic indicators will lead to the estimation of overall eco-efficiency of the product, and will guide the optimization of the production process, with the aim to maximize its eco-efficiency, either by reducing the environmental impact or by increasing the economic output, arising from the applied processes and materials used.

Figure 1. VALIAS Ecosystem.

3. Results and Discussion

VALIAS Innovation

The main Research and Innovation (RI) objectives of VALIAS are four (1-4) and will be accomplished through six key milestones (i-vi) as presented:

	RI #1	RI #2	RI #3	RI #4
	Develop new valorization pathways of IAS creating new strategies towards their population management and preservation of European marine biodiversity	Create a new, and more importantly, sustainable source of natural safe and stable ingredients that can be integrated at an industrial level within the food, feed and cosmeceutical supply chain	Cover the consumers' demand for chemical free, natural and sustainable products	Empowering and improve the productivity of European fisheries, aquaculture, food and cosmetic sector with environmental, economic and social acceptance
i	Enrichment of the knowledge of the biological requirements of the species which is a key objective of European Directive 1143/2014 on the prevention and management of introduction and spread of at least six alien species.			
ii	Optimizing the recovery of valuable compounds from selected IAS through green extraction methods and their isolation in high purity. VALIAS targets to yielding higher than 40% and purity higher than 80%.			
iii	Encapsulation of bioactive compounds in order to increase their bioactivity and controlled release, developing stable and safe formulations. VALIAS targets encapsulation efficiency higher than 85% and controlled release of the desired bioactive agents during the consumption of final products.			
iv	Incorporation of encapsulated bioactive agents into the conventional food, feed and cosmetic production line in order to develop innovative functional products under the requirements and specifications of EU legislation. Development of at least 3 types of food products, 1 aquafeed functional premix, 1 cosmeceutical anti-aging formulation.			
v	Evaluation of the bioactive content, stability and shelf life of the final products. Implementation of market research and investigation of the commercialization potential of final products.			
vi	Sustainability Assessment and Economic evaluation of valorization pathways.			

VALIAS Outputs

To effectively manage marine European Invasive Alien Species (IAS) populations, it is essential to develop a comprehensive strategy that utilizes sustainable methods to make use of this neglected natural resource. The objective of this initiative is to establish a reliable and lasting supply of natural ingredients that are both safe and stable. These ingredients will be easily incorporated into the industrial food, feed, and cosmeceutical supply chain, thereby enabling the production of secure and stable functional food, fish feed, and cosmetic products.

In order to achieve this, optimization efforts focus on employing environmentally friendly extraction technologies to selectively retrieve marine-derived components and encapsulating techniques to enhance the effectiveness of these components and provide a controlled release of bioactive compounds. This leads to the development of safe and reliable goods.

In addition, this approach involves establishing a novel fishery, which provides economic advantages to skilled fishes, thus harmonizing ecological sustainability with financial success.

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